

Entropy and Its Association With a Physical Interaction

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In a previous note (1), we argued that an entropy function could be written as $F(p(e_i))$, where $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + \text{constant}$ (for the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$). We stated that given that the constraints represent an average 0th and first moment of e_i , $F(p(e_i))$ must be statistically consistent so $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$. We then found two solutions, i.e. $F(p) = \ln(p)$ and $F(p) = (1-p)^{1-q} / (1-q)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) and Tsallis solutions. We noted that the MB case is associated with a very specific kind of interaction, namely one that satisfies: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. The Tsallis distribution does not satisfy this expression. Even though we did not explicitly consider interaction specifics in (1), they are associated with the solutions which arise from maximization of entropy subject to constraints.

In this note, we try to investigate further the link between entropy and interaction by examining Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases. For these, it is as if one has two probabilities in the problem, i.e. $p, 1-p$ in the FD case and $p, 1+p$ in the BE. We try to determine how one would create entropy in such a case. We suggest that given the two probabilities, called $p(e_i)$ and $g(p(e_i))$, one cannot treat one with special preference. We argue that it is key to first establish: $F(p) + g(p) G(p) = -e_i/T$ and from this one may construct an appropriate entropy. It turns out that the entropy expressions differ for the FD and BE cases, i.e. $p F \mp g G(g)$.

One may then vary this with respect to either p or g and obtain the same result. We note that $g(p)$ is known a priori and that the idea of negative entropy arises in this viewpoint. We note that in this case, entropy is explicitly linked to interaction details while the constraints are not.

Statistical Averages of Moments and Hidden Information of Interaction

In (1), we suggested that if one uses constraints which are moments of e_i (i.e. e_i to the power 0 and e_i to the power 1), then this is a statistical description of a physical system based on average moments without introducing any other information (i.e. what kind of interactions occur etc). We further suggested that constraints contain two pieces of information, namely the moment information and $p(e_i)$. We suggested that one could consolidate everything into an information function

$$F(p(e_i)) \quad (1)$$

If one writes: $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ then this is also an average moment description because $F(p(e_i))$ is ultimately a function of e_i/T . We argued in (1) that this average moment description cannot have more moment information than the constraints, hence:

$$F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b \quad (2)$$

((2)), however, does not show all of the information that is contained in $F(p(e_i))$, we argue because ((2)) is only concerned with average moments. We showed in (1), that if one minimizes average information $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ (or maximizes $- p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$) subject to the constraints, then one obtains two solutions:

$F = \ln(p(e_i))$ the Maxwell–Boltzmann case ((3a))

$F = (1 - p(e_i)^q)^{1/q}$ the Tsallis case ((3b))

The MB case is directly connected with interaction information, i.e.

$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ ((4))

((4)) does not hold for the Tsallis case. Even though one compares $F(p)$ to the constraints ((2)), F can contain information about the specific interactions in the system. In other words, part of the information (e_i average moments) is contained in the constraints, while specific interaction information (in terms of $p(e_i)$'s) may be contained within $F(p(e_i))$. As a result, $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ (or minus entropy) is an important information based function.

We try to apply these ideas to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases.

Interaction Information Within the Information Function (and hence within Entropy)

Given a Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein gas, there exists an average energy. One may ask: What is the average energy and what is the probability $p(e_i)$? There may, however, be more information present than simply average momentum information. In particular, one might know something about the interaction in such a case. For example,

((5a)) If e_i interacts, there should be a $p(e_i)$ factor present, just as in the Bose-Einstein case ((4)).

((5b)) It is possible that there is a second probability (a function $g(p(e_i))$) also present in the interaction. For example, an e_i has a probability to interact proportional to $p(e_i)$, but if another e_j is trying to move into an e_i level, then there is a hindering probability $1 - p(e_i)$ for a Fermi-Dirac gas, but an enhancing factor of $1 + p(e_i)$, for a Bose-Einstein gas.

We thus suggest that two probabilities are associated with the interaction and that one knows a priori a function linking the two, i.e.

$g(p(e_i)) = 1 - p(e_i)$ for the FD case and $g(p(e_i)) = 1 + p(e_i)$ for the BE case ((6))

Based on the previous section, this interaction information should be contained in an information function as overall one describes the case by:

Sum over i $p(e_i) = 1$ and Sum over i $e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((7))

The problem is that there are two probabilities and one should not treat one with bias. We consider the information:

$$F(p(e_i)) + G(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T \quad ((8)) \quad \text{where we use } -e_i/T \text{ for } ((2))$$

A priori, one would expect that G should be +/- F because of the form of g(p) ((6)). Given that the probabilities act on different sides of a balance equation, one might expect a minus sign, i.e.

$$p(e_1) (1 -/+ p(e_3)) p(e_2) (1 -/+ p(e_4)) = p(e_3) (1 -/+ p(e_1)) p(e_4) (1 -/+ p(e_2)) \quad ((9))$$

One must create an entropy function which yields the correct distribution upon extremization using p or alternatively g.

$$\text{For the FD case: } p F(p) - g(p) G(g(p)) \text{ works } ((10a))$$

$$\text{For the BE case } p F(p) + g(p) G(g(p)) \text{ works } ((10b))$$

It is not entirely simple to create the entropy because even though it is an average of the information function, one has to worry about signs. There are two minus sign issues. One is linked with $g = 1 -/+ p$ and the other with $p(e_i)$ appearing on both sides of ((9)). The minus versus plus in ((10a)) and ((10b)) is due to $1-p$ versus $1+p$.

We note that the idea of maximization of entropy is to take the d/dp derivative of entropy to obtain the information function ((8)). If one considers $G = -F$, then entropy should follow from:

$$\text{Integral } dp F(p) - \text{Integral } F(1 -/+ p) \quad \text{where } F = \ln(p), \text{ the MB result. } ((10c))$$

Given that: $\text{Integral } \ln(p) dp = p \ln(p) - 1$, one has:

$$p \ln(p) + (1-p) \ln(1-p) \text{ for the FD case, and } p \ln(p) - (1+p) \ln(1+p) \quad ((10d))$$

As a result, interaction information is present within the information function, and ultimately information function(s) are linked with average e_i moments, but one must be careful when constructing entropy.

It seems that the information statement ((2)) is perhaps more fundamental than the entropy one because it is needed in order to create the correct entropy expression. Then:

$$p dF/dp -/+ g(P) dG/dg dg/dp = \text{constant } ((11)) \quad -/+ \quad (- \text{FD}) (+ \text{BE})$$

The constant is different in the FD and BE cases, but both lead to:

$$G(g(p)) = -\ln(g(p)) \quad ((12))$$

Thus, it seems that because $g(p)$ is on the RHS of the balance equation ((9)), it represents negative information.

Conclusion

In (1), we suggested that using average e_i moments as constraints (e_i power 0 and e_i power 1) is a statistical way of describing a physical system (e.g. average test scores). We also argued that one may try to consolidate all information in an information function $F(p)$ and create an average information $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. Given that $F(p(e_i))$ is ultimately a function of e_i/T , one cannot have this average represent more average moments than the constraint, hence $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$. One may then minimize information subject to the constraints, i.e. $p \frac{dF}{dp} = \text{constant}$ to find two solutions, $F = \ln(p)$ (Maxwell-Boltzmann case) or $F = 1/(1-q) (1 - p \text{ power } (1-q))$ (Tsallis case). The MB case involves particular interactions (i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$). Thus, the information may contain embedded interaction information which is kept separate from the average moments of the constraint.

We try to apply these ideas to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases for which there are two probabilities $p(e_i)$ and $1-p(e_i)$. We suggest that the key first equation is $F(p) + G(g(p)) = -e_i/T$ and that one may construct an appropriate entropy expression from this, i.e. $p F(p) - g(p) G(g(p))$ for the FD case and $p F(p) + g(p) G(g(p))$ for the BE case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Maximum Entropy Approach (preprint, zenodo, 2026)